

A Perspective on Time for Decay-Information

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Abstract—Quantum computer is getting into the stage of experimental deployment. However, successful quantum deployment on a macro-scale cannot be supported in the existing computer architecture and quantum technology because the performance of the quantum mechanics system with massive scale remains unknown. Considering the time-scale, we show a perspective of decay-information to insight the fundamental behavior hidden behind the quantum mechanics. In this letter, we uniquely analyze the entropy-time performance of a message and show the insight into the decaying nature of information with time.

Index Terms—Time, decay-information, quantum computer

I. INTRODUCTION

QUANTUM computer and strong artificial intelligence are the next-generation technology in the 21 century. And the premise of successful strong artificial intelligence is the beyond imagination computer power, which can not work in the state-of-art computer technology and architecture. Hence, the quantum computer as an out of box exploration is getting into the stage of experimental deployment.

However, the successful quantum deployment on a macro-scale cannot be supported in the existing computer and even quantum technology because the performance of the quantum mechanics system with massive scale remains unknown. Remarkable efforts include the strong law of large numbers and the convergence with probability one [1], information theory [2] and stochastic processes [3] which will be useful to develop the proposed mechanism and theoretical foundation in this paper.

In this letter, we propose a perspective of decay information with time sequence to insight the foundation behavior hidden behind the quantum mechanics and uniquely analyze the entropy-time performance of a particle and show the insight of the decaying nature of information with time.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We want to develop the model for one particle with one-dimensional random walk in space and another one-dimensional forward moving in the continuous-time process, where the particle is observed at $t = n\Delta t$ shown in Fig.1 and there are multiple hidden states between the two observing states.

III. ONE PARTICLE

We define a time sequence of discrete random variable $\{X_t; t = n\Delta t \text{ and } n \geq 0\}$ as the probability of particle moving in the information region denoted as $\Delta\sigma$ on the

Fig 1: Time is a sequence partially observed or approximately fully observed, where the information for the particle decay with time.

sample space Ω . Based on the second law of thermodynamics (i.e. the total entropy of an isolated system can never decrease over time), the expectation of the random variable has X_t finite expectation and $\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{E}[|X_t|] \leq \infty$.

For any $\alpha > 0$ and any integer $m \geq 1$, the Markov inequality says that

$$\Pr \left\{ \sum_{t=0}^m |X_t| > \alpha \right\} \leq \frac{\mathbb{E}[\sum_{t=0}^m |X_t|]}{\alpha} = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^m \mathbb{E}[|X_t|]}{\alpha}. \quad (1)$$

Since $|X_t|$ is non-negative, $|X_t| > \alpha$ implies that $\sum_{t=0}^m |X_t| > \alpha$. That's both sides have a limit for

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \Pr \left\{ \sum_{t=0}^m |X_t| > \alpha \right\} \leq \frac{\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{E}[|X_t|]}{\alpha}. \quad (2)$$

To bring the (2) inside the probability, we define

$$A_m = \left\{ \omega: \sum_{t=0}^m |X_t(\omega)| > \alpha \right\}. \quad (3)$$

The sequence of set is nested. Base on the axioms of probability, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \Pr \left\{ \sum_{t=0}^m |X_t| > \alpha \right\} &= \Pr \left\{ \cup_{m=1}^{\infty} A_m \right\} \\ &= \Pr \left\{ \omega: \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} |X_t| > \alpha \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Combining (3) to (4), we have

$$\Pr \left\{ \omega: \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} |X_t(\omega)| \leq \alpha \right\} \geq 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{E}[|X_t|]}{\alpha}. \quad (5)$$

Because $\{|X_t(\omega)|\}$ is a sequence of non-negative numbers with a finite sum, the individual numbers in that sequence is approaching to zero. Hence, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr \left\{ \omega: \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} |X_t(\omega)| = 0 \right\} &\geq \Pr \left\{ \omega: \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} |X_t| \leq \alpha \right\} \\ &\geq 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{E}[|X_t|]}{\alpha} \stackrel{\alpha \rightarrow \infty}{\rightarrow} 1. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Base on the information theory, we define $X_t = P(Y)$ as the probability mass function of Y , where Y is a random variable. Hence, we have

$$H(Y) = -\mathbb{E}[\log(X_t)]. \quad (7)$$

Let H be a real value function of a real variable that is continuous at zero, we have

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} H(X_t) = H(0) = 0, \text{ WP1}, \quad (8)$$

which shows the decay nature of information with time.

IV. FOUNDATION BEHAVIOR OF QUANTUM MECHANICS

The entropy is useful as a bridge between the micro-scale and macro-scale. Hence, we use the entropy-time perspective to see the hidden behavior of the quantum mechanics.

Let's treat the time-scale as a huge steel-spring. When the observer and particle are in the similarity reference system, we can compress the time-scale steel-spring and approximate the system as a fully observed time sequence system, which is known as the Newtonian system. When the observer and particle are in a totally different reference system, the time-scale steel-spring is in a stretch state and the time sequence partly observed system is known as the quantum mechanics, where the multiple hidden states can't be observed and the result in observe state is probability form. Due to the multiple hidden states can't be observed and the result in observe state will be shown in probability form. Besides, the relative theory exchange the observer reference system and particle reference system, which is impressive.

V. QUANTUM COMPUTER

The experiment proves that quantum mechanics is still a good solution for the micro-scale problem [4] because the mass of the earth influences the correlation reference systems with similar observer interval in time-scale. Hence, we should build a quantum computer for the next generation of technology, which is the focus of this section. Having the background of foundation behavior of quantum mechanics, the only way for us to control a quantum system in a macro-scale is to narrow the gap from the observer reference system and an observed particle reference system. We have instinctively three-method. First, the observer is moving fast like the particle such as light quantum. Second, we can use the duality of kelvin degree and space-scale to approaching the particle reference system with ultra-low kelvin temperature. Third, we keep observing particle at enough time and drink some coffee, then we can use the statistical theory to get the approximation results.

Hence, personally, the initial deployment position is the earth orbit. We should build the quantum computers on the orbit and keep them close to the absolute zero, which slow the decay of information on Δt and increase the information entropy by increase information region $\Delta\sigma$.

VI. REMARK

The letter shows the perspective of time from decay-information. Personally, I don't like adding too many values in science like some academic factions. I want to share the gift with you, my friends. Because we are still babies for the earth. And we are family and live in the same spaceship. There are friends and beasts in the universe as dark forest. We are never alone, show respect and move forward with peace and love.

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